

The Role of Environmental Knowledge in The Relationship Between Green Product, Green Price, Green Promotion to Green Purchase Intention in Nggela Adat Settlement, Ende District

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Abstract:- This study aims to describe green product, green price, green promotion, environmental knowledge and green purchase intention. Analyze the role of green purchases, green prices, green-promotions on green purchase intentions through environmental knowledge towards tourists in the Nggela traditional shooting. The population and sample in this study used the hair method for visitors to Nggela customary services, namely 130 tourists. Analysis technique using path analysis. The results show that green product has a significant effect on green purchase intention through environmental knowledge. While green prices have no influence on green purchase intention through environmental knowledge. For green promotion has a significant effect on green purchase intention through environmental knowledge.

Keywords:- Green Product; Green Price; Green Promotion; Environmental Knowledge; Green Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The level of tourist visits to Indonesia from year to year tends to continue to increase. This proves that the tourism sector is a market-driven industry, so there are many opportunities to market tourism products in Indonesia. Of course, in marketing this tourism product, it cannot be alone but needs the involvement of all parties, starting from tourism managers, government and local communities. The tourism sector must provide added value by getting a touch of science, technology and information starting from market analysis. To analyze the tourism market, information is needed. This information processing is closely related to consumer behavior. When information has been obtained, of course, in marketing it, a strategy is needed that is able to attract tourists (Setiawan, 2017).

This is the case with Ende Regency, which is one of the regencies in East Nusa Tenggara Province that has natural attractions such as beaches, waterfalls and interesting historical and cultural tourism that is still maintained authenticity until now. The Lio tribe is famous for its ikat weaving and the use of tools and materials from nature, which are used in settlement activities. The Nggela traditional settlement is the location of the research destination where the community's daily activities are in the surrounding environment with activities in the form of farming carried out by men and weaving carried out by women. The Nggela indigenous settlement became a fostered village with a flagship product of ikat weaving that uses materials from nature.

The community's ikat weaving products are of very high quality and have participated in the Women International Club exhibition at JCC Senayan, Jakarta in 2019. However, the knowledge and intention to buy products is still very minimal because the community and the government do not conduct socialization and counseling related to their products even though they have very strong environmental and cultural values. To support these community activities, environmental knowledge is expected to play an important role in the relationship between green product, green price and green promotion in order to influence purchasing intention or green purchase intention in the Nggela Customary Settlement.

Green product is a product that is designed to reduce the environmental impact of the product. Green price is a fair price for green products compared to conventional products. Green promotion is a promotional method used to increase buyer awareness and interest in buying green products. Environmental knowledge is a series of ecological knowledge possessed by individuals about the environment (Chen, 2013). Knowledge can affect how consumers make decisions to purchase environmentally friendly products where consumers will collect data and organize the information obtained to

evaluate a product or service (Syahbandi, 2012). Consumers must know the impact or consequences that will occur on the environment so that it does not get worse, and be responsible for further development in order to avoid adverse impacts that will occur for future generations. If consumers have knowledge about environmental issues, their level of awareness will increase and thus will potentially promote a favorable attitude towards environmentally friendly products (Aman et al., 2012). Apart from paying attention to the knowledge side of a person, the intention to purchase environmentally friendly products is also influenced by a person's attitude and the social environment can influence a person's lifestyle in using a product.

Environmental knowledge can influence the use of green products. However, there are still few studies that explore the role of environmental knowledge in the relationship between green product, green price, and green promotion on green purchase intention in the Nggela traditional settlement, Ende Regency. Therefore, the thesis with the title "The Role of Environmental Knowledge on the Relationship between Green Product, Green Price, and Green Promotion on Green Purchase Intention in the Nggela Customary Settlement, Ende Regency" will discuss the role of environmental knowledge in influencing the purchase intention or use of green products in the Nggela customary settlement. This research will use a quantitative approach using a questionnaire as a data collection tool. Respondents in this study are tourists who visit the Nggela traditional settlement and have experience buying green products. The collected data will be analyzed using the classical assumption method to test the relationship between the research variables.

It is hoped that the results of this study can provide a better understanding of the factors that influence purchasing intentions of Green Product, Green Price and Green Promotion in the Nggela Traditional Settlement and the importance of Environmental Knowledge in the development of Green Marketing in Indonesia. In addition, the results of this study can also provide input for producers and the government in increasing public awareness of the importance of Green Product, Green Price, Green Promotion and the environment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Environment Knowledge

According to Chen (2013: 27) states that environmental knowledge is a series of ecological knowledge possessed by individuals about the environment. The better the environmental knowledge possessed by consumers, the more these consumers will know about the quality of environmentally friendly products and will increase their motivation to buy environmentally friendly products. Knowledge about the environment is a basic knowledge possessed by a person regarding everything that can be done and attempted to assist in environmental protection by facilitating their behavioral commitment to purchasing green products.

B. Green Marketing

According to Polonsky (1994) green marketing includes all activities made in order to facilitate exchange activities to fulfill human wants and needs with minimal impact on the natural environment. Consumption activities carried out by humans basically damage the natural environment, so through the application of green marketing consumers hope that companies can at least reduce harmful activities that can damage the natural environment.

C. Green Product

Green products are products that do not pollute the environment, do not waste resources, and can be recycled. Green products are made in order to improve and maintain the natural environment through saving and resources and minimizing the use of hazardous substances (Shabani et al., 2013).

D. Green Price

According to Hashem and Al-Rifai (2011) green price is defined as the price determined by the company in accordance with the company's policies related to environmental considerations that are applied in accordance with the company's initiatives towards the environment. In general, green products incur greater initial costs for research and development, but in the long run it will be an economical choice and save expenses for the company. Price is the key to green products.

E. Green Place

Place is related to time and location so companies need to consider choosing the right location so that customer time can be utilized appropriately. A convenient place has a high impact on product promotion because customers want a convenient place to buy their products or services (Hossain et al., 2020). Green place is related to management to minimize the transportation emissions produced, so as to reduce the carbon footprint and pollution caused to the environment in general (Shil, 2012).

F. Green Promotion

Green promotion refers to providing real information about products in a way that does not harm consumers' interests (Hashem & Al-Rifai, 2011). Green promotion involves organizing promotional strategies such as advertising, marketing facilities, posters, sales promotion, public relations, social media marketing and on-site promotion, as well as videos and presentations (Shil, 2012). Green promotion provides information about the efforts made by companies related to environmental commitment to consumers (Fan & Zeng, 2011). The purpose of green advertising is to influence consumers regarding their purchasing behavior to choose to buy products that are not harmful to the environment and provide direction regarding their interest in the positive consequences of purchasing green products for themselves and the environment (Rahbar & Wahid, 2011).

G. Green Purchase Intention

Green Purchase Intention refers to the willingness of consumers to buy environmentally friendly products expressed by consumers by having a motive to buy them (Chan, 2001). According to Nik Abdul Rashid (2009), Green Purchase Intention is a possibility and willingness of an individual to choose environmentally friendly products over conventional products in their purchasing considerations

(Aman et al., 2012). According to Qader and Zainuddin (2011), Green Purchase Intention is a plan from an individual to engage in several actions at a specific time and opportunity to be able to behave environmentally friendly (Aman et al., 2012). Six years later it was said that Green Purchase Intention is an individual's basis for measuring behavior contained in behavioral research on the environment (Jaiswal & Kant, 2018).

III. RESEARCH CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig. 1. Research Conceptual Framework Source: Various articles, processed (2019)

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

➤ This research focuses on the study of Tourism, specifically:

Green Product, Green Price and Green Promotion in Nggela Traditional Settlement and the importance of Environmental Knowledge in the development of Green Marketing in Indonesia. This research is an explanatory research, the location of this research was conducted in Ende Regency. Nggela Traditional Village is located in one of the sub-districts in Ende Regency, namely Wolojita District. The population in this study were all visitors to the Nggela traditional village with an unknown number and the sample was used with the opinion of Pendap at Prawira (2010: 46) if the population is unknown then determining the sample size then the method becomes very sensitive so it is difficult to get good goodness of fit measures. So it is recommended that the minimum sample size is 5-10 observations for each parameter being estimated. So that because in this study there were 13 statements, the number of samples was determined to be $10 \times 13 = 130$ respondents. The data analysis technique uses Descriptive Statistical Analysis, Multiple linear regression analysis with 2 models, and Hypothesis Testing.

V. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF VARIABLES

A. Green product:

A product that is friendly or harmless to the environment, either during the production process or when consuming it. Green Product indicators are: 1) Product raw materials, 2) Product packaging.

B. Green Price

The price offered by the company for the green product offered. Green Price indicators are: 1) Increased product costs, 2) Increased product value.

C. Green Promotion

A process of introducing environmentally friendly products to the public with various actions or actions that are environmentally friendly. Indicators of Green Promotion are, 1) Advertising and / or promotion that cares about the environment, 2) Advertising and promotion of procedures related to the environment and 3) Environmental action advertising.

D. Environmental Knowledge

Individual knowledge and awareness of environmental issues when individuals are equipped with sufficient environmental knowledge, the greater the environmentally friendly behavior carried out by these individuals Environmental Knowledge indicators are: 1) Knowledge about the environment, 2) Consumer awareness and 3) Environmental regulations.

E. Green Purchase Intention

Purchase intention and real purchases by consumers after they realize the existence of environmentally friendly attributes on a brand Indicators of Green Purchase Intention are: 1) Product quality, 2) The surrounding environment and 3) Trust in the product.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 130 respondents filled out this research questionnaire online. The results of the hypothesis analysis of each path obtained from the results of path analysis using SPSS software are as follows:

A. Demographic Statistics

TABLE I. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Item	Optional	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	49	37,7
	Female	81	62,3
Age	15-20 Years	13	10,0
	21-30 Years	86	66,2
	31-40 Years	27	20,8
	>41 Years	4	3,1
Education level	High School	24	18,5
	Diploma	12	9,2
	S1	84	64,6
	S2	9	6,9
	S3	1	0,8

B. Regression Analysis Model 1

Model Equation 1 → $Y_1 = \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e_1$

TABLE II. PATH TEST RESULTS REGRESSION ANALYSIS MODEL I

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	-.082	.723		-.113	.910
<i>Green_Product</i>	.101	.047	.065	2.160	.033
<i>Green_Price</i>	-.093	.049	-.072	-1.895	.060
<i>Green_Promotion</i>	1.013	.033	.987	30.263	.000
Dependent Variable	<i>Environmental_Knowledge</i>				
R	0,971				
R ²	0,943				
R ² Adjusted	0,942				
F Count	696,048				
Probability	0				
Line Equation 1	$Y_1 = \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e_1$				
Result	$Y_1 = 0.065 + (-0.072) + 0.987 + e_1$				

Source: Primary data, processed (2023)

In this study, the first model regression results show a significant value of Green Product (X1) = 0.033 Green Price (X2) = 0.060 and Green Promotion (X3) = 0.000 which means that of the three variables above, Green Product and Green Promotion have a significant effect while Green Price has no effect on Environmental Knowledge. While the R Square or R² number is 0.943, which means that the contribution of Green Product, Green Price and Green Promotion to Environmental Knowledge reaches 94%. Then for the regression results show that the F count is 696.048 with a significance of 0.000, which means that all independent variables equally affect Environmental Knowledge. The regression results obtained $Y_1 = 0.065 + (-0.072) + 0.987 + e_1$

VII. HYPOTHESIS TEST

TABLE III. CALCULATION OF DIRECT, INDIRECT AND TOTAL EFFECTS

Variable	Direct Influence	Sig.	Indirect Influence	Total Influence	Information
Green Product (X ₁) – Environmental Knowledge(Y ₁)	.065	.033			Significant
Green Price (X ₂) – Environmental Knowledge(Y ₁)	-.072	.060			Not Significant
Green Promotion (X ₃) – Environmental Knowledge(Y ₁)	.987	.000			Signifikan
Green Product (X ₁) – Green Purchase Intention (Y ₂)	.084	.282			Not Significant
Green Price (X ₂) – Green Purchase Intention (Y ₂)	.261	.008			Signifikan
Green Promotion (X ₃) – Green Purchase Intention (Y ₂)	-.232	.330			Not Significant
Environmental Knowledge (Y ₁) – Green Purchase Intention (Y ₂)	.757	.001			Not Significant
Green Product (X ₁) – Environmental Knowledge (Y ₁) – Green Purchase Intention (Y ₂)			0.065 x 0.757 = 0.049	0.084 + 0.049 = 0.133	Indirect influence > Direct influence 0,133 > 0,084 means strengthen
Green Price (X ₂) – Environmental Knowledge (Y ₁) – Green Purchase Intention (Y ₂)			-0.72 x 0.757 = -0.054	0.261 + -0.054 = 0.207	Indirect influence > Direct influence 0,207 > 0,261 means unstrengthen
Green Promotion (X ₃) – Environmental Knowledge (Y ₁) – Green Purchase Intention (Y ₂)			0.987 x 0.757 = 0.747	-0.232 + 0.747 = 0.515	Indirect influence > Direct influence 0,515 > -0,232 means strengthen

The direct effect between *Green Product* (X₁) on *Green Purchase Intention* (Y₂) is 0.084 while the indirect effect through *Environmental Knowledge* (Y₁) is 0.133, from this it can be seen that 0.133 > 0.084 which means that the *Environmental Knowledge* variable (Y₁) **strengthens the relationship** between the *Green Product* variable (X₁) and *Green Purchase Intention* (Y₂). The direct effect of *Green Price* (X₂) on *Green Purchase Intention* (Y₂) is 0.261 while the indirect effect through *Environmental Knowledge* (Y₁) is 0.207, from this it can be seen that 0.207 < 0.261 which means that the variable *Environmental Knowledge* (Y₁) **does not strengthen the relationship** between the variable *Green Price* (X₂) and *Green Purchase Intention* (Y₂). While the direct effect of *Green Promotion* (X₁) on *Green Purchase Intention* (Y₂) is -0.232 while the indirect effect through *Environmental Knowledge* (Y₁) is 0.515, from here it can be seen that -0.232 > 0.515 which means that the variable *Environmental Knowledge* (Y₁) **strengthens the relationship**

between the variable *Green Promotion* (X₃) and *Green Purchase Intention* (Y₂).

VIII. DISCUSSION

A. Effect of *Green Product* (X₁) on *Environmental Knowledge* (Y₁).

Green product has a significant effect on environmental knowledge in the Nggela Traditional Settlement, Ende Regency. One important indicator that triggers the influence of green products on environmental knowledge is raw materials derived from natural materials that are environmentally friendly and can be recycled in accordance with the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle). The importance of raw materials as the main factor of production. Consumers need to identify the components in the Kelimara traditional weaving production process. From this, it is increasingly convincing consumers to choose traditional Kelimara weaving products as a result of good public knowledge to buy

environmentally friendly traditional weaving. The results of this study support Dangelico (2010) who proved that raw materials provide recycled functionality and have environmentally friendly properties.

B. The effect of Green Price (X2) on Environmental Knowledge (Y1).

Green Price has no significant effect on environmental knowledge in the Nggela Traditional Settlement, Ende Regency. This means that even though the green price on traditional Kelimara weaving products in the Nggela Traditional Settlement has used natural materials taken from the surrounding environment, consumers do not know the green price that supports it. Although the selling price of the product is maximized, the purchase price of the product is appropriate, and it is beneficial to the community because it uses natural materials, it is not enough for consumers because the weaving material is relatively cheap and the quality of the product is guaranteed, it has not fostered buying intentions or recommendations to buy to others. In accordance with Amin's research (2023) which states that the high price because the product is environmentally friendly, the decision to buy traditional woven Kelimara products is decreasing. So it remains important to develop and increase knowledge about natural materials so that the price of woven products is of high value.

C. The effect of Green Promotion (X3) on Environmental Knowledge (Y1).

The results of Green Promotion (X3) research have an effect on environmental knowledge (Y1). This means that environmentally friendly advertisements, procedures that show environmental care and environmental action in advertisements have a good influence on the good impression on consumers and tourists. In line with Rahbar (2011) environmentally friendly advertising affects consumers regarding purchasing behavior. Where marketing and promotion are carried out by the community so that it helps consumers to increasingly know the role of environmental knowledge in Kelimara weaving products.

D. The effect of Environmental Knowledge (Y1) on Green Purchase Intention (Y2).

Based on the research results, Environmental Knowledge (Y1) affects Green Purchase Intention (Y2). This means that knowledge of environmentally friendly products, consumer awareness and environmental regulations in the production process of Kelimara weaving in the Nggela traditional settlement affect purchase intention. In line with Wijayanti's research (2019) having knowledge about the environment will have a significant influence on green purchase intention. Environmental knowledge as a basic knowledge of each individual regarding everything that can be done to help protect the environment. Similarly, Andryani (2015) says that the higher the knowledge of each individual about the environment they have, it will change individual behavior in dealing with environmental problems.

E. The effect of Green Product (X1) on Green Purchase Intention (Y2).

Based on the results of the analysis of green product on green purchase intention has no effect. This means that even though the raw materials and packaging of traditional Kelimara weaving are known to use natural materials and can be reused, reused and recycled, it is not enough to increase consumer buying intentions. In accordance with Setyabudi's research (2020) which says that even though consumers have good knowledge of green products without trust or confidence, it will have an impact on the environment and buying interest does not arise.

F. The effect of Green Price on Green Purchase Intention (Y2).

Based on the results of the study, it shows that green price has an effect on green purchase intention. This means that the cost and value of traditional Kelimara weaving makes consumers interested and intend to buy. The relatively cheap and efficient cost of traditional Kelimara weaving does not make the purchase price and selling price minimal because it is seen from the quality and benefits obtained from this product. In accordance with Laroche's research (2001) if consumers believe the price is reasonable then they will buy the product. In addition, consumers are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products. People with a high awareness of the environment will be price sensitive and willing to pay a premium.

G. The effect of Green Promotion on Green Purchase Intention (Y2).

Based on the results of the study, it shows that green promotion has an effect on green purchase intention. This means that the advertisements and promotions of Kelimara traditional weaving are environmentally friendly because they use electronic media, social media and counseling with environmental actions. Marketing of traditional woven fabrics while campaigning for environmentally friendly things so that it affects green purchase intention. The counseling from related parties such as the environmental service, OPD to traditional leaders (Mosalaki) which makes consumers confident and intend to buy. In accordance with Ansar's research (2013) conducting sharp advertising and promotional campaigns will convey effective messages about green attributes and will increase consumer buying intentions. Menon's research results (1999) say promotional campaigns are used to communicate with consumers to switch to green products. Most stores use environmental awareness for their brand promotion.

H. The effect of Green Product (X1) on Green Purchase Intention (Y2) through Environmental Knowledge (Y1).

In this study, it is known that there is an influence between green product on green purchase intention through environmental knowledge. Environmental knowledge is able to strengthen the relationship between green product and green purchase intention. Although initially green product has no effect on green purchase intention, it becomes influential because it is strengthened by environmental knowledge. The existence of raw materials and packaging has not made consumers understand that the ingredients used are

environmentally friendly. Conversely, if consumers understand that the natural ingredients used are taken from nature and even from the garden of the Nggela indigenous settlement community, it can bring new knowledge and create a positive purchase intention. Likewise in Irawati and Suparna's research (2015) which states that knowledge of products has a positive but insignificant effect on the purchase intention of environmentally friendly products. This happens if you only have knowledge without the support of other variables, it is not enough to influence consumer intention to buy environmentally friendly products.

I. The effect of Green Price (X2) on Green Purchase Intention (Y2) through Environmental Knowledge (Y1).

In this study, it is known that there is an influence between green price on green purchase intention through environmental knowledge. However, green price can affect green purchase intention directly. Although initially green price has no effect on environmental knowledge, the role of green purchase intention makes green price influential because of trust in products, quality that pays attention to the surrounding environment so that it makes the green price value high. Similarly, research by Setyabudi and Adialita (2020) states that when consumers' understanding of environmental attributes and environmental impacts is high on products, their trust is higher. So that consumers who have confidence in environmentally friendly products will have an interest in buying.

J. The effect of Green Promotion (X3) on Green Purchase Intention (Y2) through Environmental Knowledge (Y1).

In this study, it is known that there is an influence between Green Promotion on Green Purchase Intention through environmental knowledge. Environmental knowledge can strengthen the relationship between Green promotion and green purchase intention. Similarly, Ansar (2013) states that environmental advertising is more effective in increasing consumer knowledge of green products and assisting in purchasing intentions. Therefore, according to Hartmann and Ibanez (2006) advertising will be able to help increase motivation to buy environmental products.

IX. CONCLUSION

From the results of the analysis and discussion, the results obtained 1) Green Product has a significant influence on Environmental Knowledge in Nggela Traditional Settlements, 2) Green Price does not have a significant influence on Environmental Knowledge at the Nggela Customary Settlement, 3) Green Promotion has a significant influence on Environmental Knowledge in the Nggela Customary Settlement. 4) Environmental Knowledge has a significant influence on Green Purchase Intention in the Nggela Customary Settlement, 5) Green Product does not have a significant influence on Green Purchase Intention in the Nggela Customary Settlement. 6) Green Price has a significant influence on Environmental Knowledge in the Nggela Customary Settlement. 7) Green Promotion has a significant influence on Environmental Knowledge in the Nggela Customary Settlement.

This research examines only the influence of variables that affect behavioral intention and behavioral usage, but does not link to usage outcomes. Sometimes it is assumed that usage will produce positive results. This assumption needs further research. In addition, to determine usage behavior, it should also be linked to existing competitive advantages. (Hidayatullah et al., 2019) because almost all banks use the Mobile banking application, but the quality of the system and the quality of information from mobile banking must also be considered. (Shodiq et al., 2018)(Rakhmadian et al., 2017), as well as paying attention to the behavior of the system users themselves where currently the millennial age is very dominant so that m banking must also adjust to the tastes of this age. (Hidayatullah et al., 2018).

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abdulwahab, L., & Dahalin, Z. M. (2010). A Conceptual Model of Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) Modification with Management Effectiveness and Program Effectiveness in Context of Telecentre. *African Scientist*.
- [2]. Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T).
- [3]. Al-Gahtani, S. S., Hubona, G. S., & Wang, J. (2007). Information technology (IT) in Saudi Arabia: Culture and the acceptance and use of IT. *Information and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2007.09.002>
- [4]. Arbie, E. (2000). *Introduction to Management Information Systems*. 7th Edition, Volume. Cahyani, E. D. (2013). Analysis of Acceptance of the Guru Room Application as a Media for
- [5]. Fulfilling Academic Information for Senior High School Students in Surabaya City Based on the Utaut2 Model. *Journal ESTY D.C*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- [6]. Fauzi, A., Widodo, T., & Djatmiko, T. (2018). The Effect of Behavioral Intention on Use Behavior on the Use of Online Transportation Applications (Case Study on Go-Jek and Grab Users Among Telkom University Students). *E-Proceeding of Management*.
- [7]. Handayani, T., & Sudiana, S. (2017). ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF THE UTAUT MODEL (UNIFIED THEORY OF ACCEPTANCE AND USE OF TECHNOLOGY) TO INFORMATION SYSTEM USER BEHAVIOR (CASE STUDY: ACADEMIC INFORMATION SYSTEM AT STTNAS YOGYAKARTA). *Angkasa: Scientific Journal of Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.28989/angkasa.v7i2.159>
- [8]. Hariyanti, A. O., Hidayatullah, S., & Prasetya, D. A. (2020a). Analysis of the Acceptance and Use of Mobile Banking Services Using the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (Case Study of. 5(1), 254-262.

- [9]. Hariyanti, A. O., Hidayatullah, S., & Prasetya, D. A. (2020b). Analysis of the Acceptance and Use of Mobile Banking Services Using the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (Case Study of Bank Jatim Pasuruan Branch). *Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science*, 5(1), 254-262.
- [10]. Hidayatullah, S., Firdiansjah, A., Patalo, R. G., & Waris, A. (2019). The effect of entrepreneurial marketing and competitive advantage on marketing performance. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*.
- [11]. Hidayatullah, S., Waris, A., & Devianti, R. C. (2018). Millennial Generation Behavior in Using the Go-Food Application. *JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP*. <https://doi.org/10.26905/jmdk.v6i2.2560>
- [12]. Indrata, S. L., Susanti, C. E., & Kristanti, M. M. (2017). The Effect of Perceived Value and E- Service Quality on Customer Behavioral Intention through Customer Satisfaction for Gojek Users in Surabaya. *Scientific Review of Management Students*.
- [13]. Ismarmiaty, I., & Etmy, D. (2018). Modified UTAUT2 Approach Model on the Analysis of Acceptance and Use of E-Government Technology in West Nusa Tenggara. *MATRIK: Journal of Management, Informatics Engineering and Computer Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.30812/matrik.v18i1.347>
- [14]. Madi, T., Dahalin, Z., & Baharom, F. (2011). Content analysis on agile values: A perception from software practitioners. 2011 5th Malaysian Conference in Software Engineering, MySEC 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MySEC.2011.6140710>
- [15]. Mustaqim, R., Kusyanti, A., & Aryadita, H. (2018). Analysis of Factors Affecting the Intention to Use XYZ E-Commerce Using the UTAUT (Unified Theory Acceptance and Use Of Technology) Model. *Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science Development*.
- [16]. Owusu Kwateng, K., Osei Atiemo, K. A., & Appiah, C. (2019). Acceptance and use of mobile banking: an application of UTAUT2. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-03-2018-0055>
- [17]. Rakhmadian, M., Hidayatullah, S., Respati, H., & Malang, U. M. (2017). Analysis of System Quality and Information Quality on User Satisfaction of Lecturer Academic Information System. *National Seminar on Information Systems*, September, 665-675.
- [18]. Research, J., & Dan, A. (2007). *Management Information System. Accounting and Business Research*.
- [19]. Rossmann, C. (2011). Theory of Reasoned Action - Theory of Planned Behavior. In *Theory of Reasoned Action - Theory of Planned Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.5771/9783845260341>
- [20]. Setyningrum, F., Arifin, Z., & Yulianto, E. (2016). INFLUENCE OF HEDONIC MOTIVES ON SHOPPING LIFESTYLE AND IMPULSE BUYING (Survey on Superindo Supermarket Consumers Who Do Impulse Buying). *Journal of Business Administration S1 Brawijaya University*.
- [21]. Shodiq, A. F., Hidayatullah, S., & Ardianto, Y. T. (2018). INFLUENCE OF DESIGN, INFORMATION QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SERVICES WEBSITE ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION. 9(12), 746-750.
- [22]. Sniehotta, F. F., Scholz, U., & Schwarzer, R. (2005). Bridging the intention-behavior gap: Planning, self-efficacy, and action control in the adoption and maintenance of physical exercise. *Psychology and Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08870440512331317670>
- [23]. Sutton, S. (2014). Theory of planned behavior. In *Cambridge Handbook of Psychology, Health and Medicine*, Second Edition. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511543579.049>
- [24]. Taiwo, A. A., & Downe, A. G. (2013). The theory of user acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT): A meta-analytic review of empirical findings. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*.
- [25]. Venkatesh, V., Morris, M., Davis, G., & Davis, F. (2003). TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL - Research. *MIS Quarterly*.
- [26]. Venkatesh, Viswanath, Brown, S. A., & Bala, H. (2013). Bridging the qualitative-quantitative divide: Guidelines for conducting mixed methods research in information systems. *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2013/37.1.02>
- [27]. Venkatesh, Viswanath, Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). Venkatesh et al (2003) User acceptance of information technology (1). *MIS Quarterly*.
- [28]. Wang, H. Y., & Wang, S. H. (2010). User acceptance of mobile internet based on the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology: Investigating the determinants and gender differences. *Social Behavior and Personality*. <https://doi.org/10.2224/sbp.2010.38.3.415>
- [29]. Warshaw, P. R., & Davis, F. D. (1985). Disentangling behavioral intention and behavioral expectation. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1031\(85\)90017-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1031(85)90017-4)